

PATIENTS OPINIONS ABOUT THE PLACEBO / NOCEBO EFFECT IN THE DOCTOR – PATIENT THERAPEUTIC RELATIONSHIP

Opinia pacienților despre efectul placebo / nocebo în relația terapeutică medic-pacient

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Rezumat. Medicina contemporană promovează ideea că modul în care medicul prescrie medicamentul este mult mai important decât medicamentul în sine, din motiv că complexitatea factorilor subiectivi ai relației terapeutice poate influența acțiunea medicamentului, perturbând efectul farmacodinamic al acestuia. În lucrare a fost aplicat chestionarul standartizat din 2 secțiuni: 1) opinii privind administrarea preparatelor placebo și 2) opinii despre rolul efectului placebo/nocebo al medicului în relația terapeutică. O treime din respondenți au perceput placebo ca o soluție pentru a obține rezultate terapeutice mai bune. Atitudinea pacienților față de administrarea medicamentului neutru în locul terapiei de bază a fost pozitivă în 78% de cazuri (în cazul când, consideră relația lor cu medicul drept una satisfăcătoare). Dar, 1/5 dintre pacienți au demonstrat o atitudine negativă față de preparatele placebo. Opiniile pacienților despre efectul placebo/nocebo în relația terapeutică pot influența și modela atât relația cu medicul, cât și tratamentul în sine.

Cuvinte-cheie: efect placebo; efect nocebo, relație terapeutică, medic-pacient.

The therapeutic relationship between the doctor and the patient is the established connection during the interactions between them in order to collaborate to solve the patient's health problems. The psychological component of the therapeutic relationship has an important role in increasing or decreasing the effectiveness of drug therapy. The placebo/nocebo effect in the therapeutic relationship must be highlighted by every health practitioner, because as the studies in the field report: “trust in the doctor is sometimes more valuable than the action of the medicine”¹. The therapeutic relationship is based on communication, and placebo or nocebo phenomena – as products of the patient's influence and suggestibility, have a well-defined place in the doctor-patient relationship. Through the given research we aimed to identify patients' views of the placebo/nocebo effect in the therapeutic relation-

¹ Chavarria, V., Vian, J., Pereira, C., Data-Franco, J., Fernandes, B. S., Berk, M., & Dodd, S. (2017). The Placebo and Nocebo Phenomena: Their Clinical Management and Impact on Treatment Outcomes. *Clinical therapeutics*, 39(3), 477–486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinthera.2017.01.031>

ship and the contributing psychological factors, as thoughts, feelings, and other cognitive characteristics that affect human attitude, behaviour, and mind functions. These factors can influence the way a person thinks and subsequently practises his decisions and relationships in his daily life.

Placebo therapies have proven effective in about 30% of cases, being used by doctors for centuries². Some researchers believe that the placebo effect is simply a psychological response to illness, and the act of administering a placebo drug instils a feeling of well-being. Other theories try to explain the placebo effect through the patient's expectations of the drug and the doctor³.

According to the synthesis made regarding the placebo/nocebo effect concepts, for the given research, we operate with the following working definitions:

- *The Placebo Effect* - the positive effect obtained only through the power of trust in the preparation⁴, without it necessarily incorporating an active substance⁵; (eg: “miracle” weight loss pills or heart-shaped pills will have a much better effect than “classic” shaped ones)⁶.

- *The Nocebo Effect* - attracting negative effects, by not trusting the preparation⁷, or believing that it will harm them (eg: if a drug has a list of side effects and the person taking the drug daily knows these reactions, it is possible to generate and amplify them with the help of their own brain)⁸.

Studies in the field show that regardless of the targeted nosologically entity, there is a whole series of psychological phenomena related to the effects of drug therapy, which can be used to the advantage or detriment of the patient. The thorough knowledge of psychological factors by the medical staff plays a primary role in determining the response of the sick body to the administration of some drugs, even those neutral from the pharmacodynamic point of view. Thus, if these details are not fully known by the doctor, the effectiveness of the prescribed therapy can be undermined or lead to the occurrence of unwanted effects⁹. That is why it is considered that the gold standard of the therapeutic relationship is the com-

² Benedetti, F., & Piedimonte, A. (2019). The neurobiological underpinnings of placebo and nocebo effects. *Seminars in arthritis and rheumatism*, 49(3S), S18–S21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semarthrit.2019.09.015>

³ Bittar, C., & Nascimento, O. J. (2015). Placebo and nocebo effects in the neurological practice. *Arquivos de neuro-psiquiatria*, 73(1), 58–63. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0004-282X20140180>

⁴ Colloca L. Placebo, nocebo, and learning mechanisms. *Handb Exp Pharmacol*. 2014; 225:17-35.

⁵ Evers, A. W. M., Colloca, L., Blease, C., Annoni, M., Atlas, L. Y., Benedetti, F., Bingel, U., Büchel, C., Carvalho, C., Colagiuri, B., Crum, A. J., Enck, P., Gaab, J., Geers, A. L., Howick, J., Jensen, K. B., Kirsch, I., Meissner, K., Napadow, V., Peerdeman, K. J., ... Kelley, J. M. (2018). Implications of Placebo and Nocebo Effects for Clinical Practice: Expert Consensus. *Psychotherapy and psychosomatics*, 87(4), 204–210. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000490354>

⁶ Enck, P., & Klosterhalfen, S. (2019). Placebos and the Placebo Effect in Drug Trials. *Handbook of experimental pharmacology*, 260, 399–431. https://doi.org/10.1007/164_2019_269

⁷ Flaten, M. A., Aslaksen, P. M., Lyby, P. S., & Bjørkedal, E. (2011). The relation of emotions to placebo responses. *Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological sciences*, 366(1572), 1818–1827. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2010.0407>

⁸ Psihologia Interventiei Terapeutice. (2024). Rasfoiesc.com. <https://www.rasfoiesc.com/educatie/psihologie/PSIHOLOGIA-INTERVENTIEI-TERAPE71.php>

⁹ Jakovljevic M. (2014). The placebo-nocebo response: controversies and challenges from clinical and research perspective. *European neuropsychopharmacology : the journal of the European College of Neuropsychopharmacology*, 24(3), 333–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.euroneuro.2013.11.014>

bination of both approaches in the treatment, namely the provision of appropriate emotional support plus the necessary pharmacological medication¹⁰.

Among the factors that determine the effect of neutral medication, according to Sprite and Simon, there are (I) the disease, (II) the patient, (III) the placebo itself, and (IV) the doctor¹¹.

a) The disease as a factor in the effects of neutral medication depends on the etiological substrate of the illness. In conditions with a higher degree of subjectivity, placebo substances achieve better results, while conditions with a clearer organicity prove to be more resistant. The disease duration also has an influence because more recent diseases with a shorter evolution are more sensitive to neutral medication, giving a positive effect, similarly, diseases with slow evolution with indicators of chronicity have a negative connotation on the patient's trust in the received medication.

b) The patient as a factor of the placebo effect is distinguished by the structure of his personality and the degree of suggestibility he demonstrates. However, it cannot be generalized that there is a certain type of personality, which would respond to a certain extent to the administration of a neutral drug, because, in addition to the patient's personality, there is also his age, gender, past experiences, etc. The variability of the response to the administration of the neutral substance is largely influenced by the patient's expectations, which are themselves determined by the doctor's attitude and his actions toward the patient.

c) The drug is a component of the therapeutic effects, even in the case when it comes to the neutral medication. The novelty especially determines the placebo effects: *i.e.* the more recently a medicine has appeared, with a new name or with intense promotion, the more it cultivates trust; preferentially with intravenous administration; pleasant, sophisticated appearance; the taste of the medicine must be pleasant, with the strong smell of medicine or herbs; colour: in anxious states – green, in depressive states – yellow, in states of irritability – blue and green. Rectal and intramuscular administration rise the probability of the nocebo effects, in addition with trivial or uncomfortable appearance; lack of smell; unpleasant taste, white or grey colour etc.

d) The doctor's characteristics related to the placebo effect are the prestige, which results from the training and the titles held by him, the administrative-medical functions, for example a patient would have more trust in a doctor who is head of department, university professor etc. In the same way, the past experiences determine his trust in an actual therapeutic relationship. Last but not least are the doctor's relational qualities, such as the friendly attitude towards the patient, human warmth, empathy, self-giving, the power of persuasion, the ability to influence through clear and reasoned messages, accompanied by examples that highlights the positive effects of the prescribed preparation.

Joe Dispenza, known for his self-healing experience that he describes in the book *You are a placebo*, mentions the fundamental idea that man, through the power of his thoughts, is the possessor of an unimaginable power – to determine down to the molecular level the biochemical processes that take place in his body. Systematizing what has been exposed,

¹⁰ Meissner K. (2022). Placebo, nocebo: Believing in the field of medicine. *Frontiers in pain research* (Lausanne, Switzerland), 3, 972169. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpain.2022.972169>

¹¹ Mostafaei, H., Jilch, S., Carlin, G. L., Mori, K., Quhal, F., Pradere, B., Laukhtina, E., Schuettfort, V. M., Aydh, A., Sari Motlagh, R., Roehrborn, C. G., Shariat, S. F., & Hajebrahimi, S. (2022). The placebo and nocebo effects in functional urology. *Nature reviews. Urology*, 19(3), 171–189. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41585-021-00545-2>

in order to get from thoughts to organic manifestations, it is necessary to follow the path: thought – neural network – neurotransmitters – epigenetic signal to the cell – activation of gene expression – protein synthesis – expression of life. Depending on the thoughts we have, different types of neural networks are activated.

Thus, if a patient creates a correct level of thinking, with clear intentions and positive emotions, the correct type of signal for DNA expression arrives at the cellular level. The received message causes the production of healthy proteins for the optimal functioning of the body and stimulates the repair of existing structural defects, the activation of pluripotent undifferentiated stem cells, which can replace damaged cells from the skin, blood, reproductive system, liver, bone system, even from the nervous system. This, as Joe Dispenza mentions, is the placebo phenomenon, which is a healing enigma of many pathologies. When a patient experiences emotion such as joy, fulfilment, delight, hope, satisfaction, a neuropeptide – oxytocin is released in his brain, which blocks the receptors for fear and anxiety. Thus, many organs contain receptors for oxytocin, and its synthesis after experiencing positive emotions has a healing effect, such as increasing the number of vessels in the heart, stimulating the immune function, increasing gastric motility, normalizing the level of glucose in the blood¹².

Based on studies demonstrating the placebo/nocebo effect, the idea emerges that the human brain acts as a real laboratory, producing its own drugs. This mysterious engineering determines the dynamics of the state of health and according to *Benedetti F.*: “the process works not because of some pill magic, but because the human body is its own best pharmacist and because the best prescriptions are filled by the body itself”.

The research was elaborated within medical university departments in collaboration with medical institution from Chisinau. Two research methods were applied: the interview and the self-administrated questionnaire. Patients were asked to respond orally to some general questions about placebo/nocebo effect in the doctor-patient therapeutic relationship, as: What the placebo/nocebo is in your opinion? What do you know about the placebo/nocebo effect? Do you believe the physician become like a placebo or nocebo for a patient?

The questionnaire was made up of two sections: the first section (10 questions) elucidated the patients' opinion about the administration of placebo preparations and the second section (10 questions) provided the patients' opinions about the role of the doctor's placebo/nocebo effect in the therapeutic relationship¹³. Before to invite patients to a questioning, they were informed about our research goal. Additionally, they were asked about agreement to use their (anonymous) responses for a statistical data analysis.

We collected data from 101 patients aged between 26 and 77 years, from the inpatient ward of a medical institution in Chisinau. The statistical self-administrated questionnaire was elaborated as an investigation tool, with the help of which, the opinions of 101 patients were collected, (50 men and 51 women), of which: 50 patients from the urology department; 20 – from the oncology and 31 from the internal medicine department from a medical institution from Chisinau. Age of respondents between 26-77 years. Educational level of pa-

¹² Dispenza, Joe (2014). *You are the placebo: making your mind matter*. Carlsbad, California: Hay House.

¹³ Ferdohleb, Alina. *Instrumente de cercetare în Sănătatea Publică : (culegere de chestionare) / Alina Ferdohleb, Cătălina Croitoru, Elena Ciobanu ; Agenția Națională pentru Sănătate Publică, Universitatea de Stat de Medicină și Farmacie „Nicolae Testemițeanu” din Republica Moldova. Chișinău: [s. n.], 2023. 140 p. Bibliogr.: p. 133-140.*

tients: 13,86% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 9,91-17,80) patients with graduated middle school, 23,76% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 19,81-27,71) patients with secondary education and 62,38% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 58,43-66,33) with higher education. Living environment of the patients: 59,41% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 55,46-63,35) of the questioned patients are urban residents and 40,59% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 36,64-44,54) representatives from the rural area. Filter questions were used to determine the degree of knowledge of the problem under discussion, closed questions regarding the patients' attitude towards the problem addressed, questions with coded multiple answers related to the same problem, dichotomous questions: true/false. The questionnaire was applied within the hospital, in face-to-face conversation with the patient. For the beginning, each patient was given clear and understandable information about the placebo/nocebo effect, later they were asked about the level of familiarity with these two notions, after, situations, in which the patients would have requested the application of the placebo therapy, were proposed to them.

Since the neutral therapy model remains a controversial topic, patients were first asked about their familiarity with the addressed topic. The obtained results show that a good part of the sampled patients knows about the placebo effect, they have encountered it during their life or heard about this term in different contexts. We suppose that this result is determined by the fact that most of the patients were with a higher educational level, suffering from chronic diseases, which led them to be interested in existing alternative treatment methods for their pathology.

As for the concept of nocebo, patients are less familiar with this term compared to the previous one. We assume that this is because a wide variety of practical studies refer to the placebo effect. The emergence of new drugs involves thorough studies with research on the results obtained after the administration of the placebo and the administration of the preparation itself. As well as much information about placebo is publicized. Studies on nocebo have been left in the shadows in recent years, as the aim is to respect the principle of non-harm to the patient and no research aims to bring harm to the patients participating in the study.

Since placebo remains a controversial subject, based on which many studies have been done over time and various experts have had different opinions about its effectiveness, finally, we would like to find out in this study as well which would be situations, in which patients would agree to use the neutral therapy model. Different circumstances have been proposed, in which patients would consent to placebo therapy.

The respondents' answers to the question "Situations or conditions in which patients accept the application of neutral therapy" structured: 1) "At your own request" – 11,88% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 19,81-27,71); 2) "To achieve better therapeutic results" – 33,66% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 29,71-37,61); 3) "As a treatment option, in the case of a disease with unknown therapy" – 13,86% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 9,91-17,81); 4) "As a substitute when standard treatments cannot be used (e.g. allergies, adverse reactions)" – 9,98% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 5,95-13,85); 5) "To strengthen the body" – 9,98% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 5,95-13,85); 6) "If the accusations and the results of the investigations cannot be attributed to a specific disease" – 7,92% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 3,98-11,87); 7) "To avoid drugs addiction" – 15,84% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 11,89-19,79) of case.

According to the obtained results, we infer the idea that a third of patients 33,66% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 29,71-37,61), see placebo, as a solution to obtain better therapeutic results, Less, for them, placebo would be a method of strengthening the body or an alternative when we cannot attribute a patient's symptoms to a concrete disease. Also, placebo remains useful in cases of avoiding drug addiction. In the case of the first option of using a placebo at one's own re-

quest, 11,88% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 8,03-15,93) of the patients believe that this would be an optimal method. But this opinion raises the question: does the placebo work when a person knows about it or not? Around 9,90% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 5,95-13,85) of patients, consider, that placebo administration remains useful even when standard therapy cannot be used. This is the case when patients do not tolerate the treatment and manifest various side effects.

After discussion about when to administrate placebo, we also need to consider how we do it. To form an image of this subject, patients were offered 4 methods, used in the practice of doctors. Thus, to the question: "In which of the following cases do you think placebo drug therapy would have more effect?" patients could select the following response options.

The "Patients' opinion about the situations in which drug therapy with placebo would have more effect was structured by: 1) "Placebo administration without notice" – 43,56% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 39,61-47,51); 2) "Placebo administration plus direct information" – 7,92% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 3,97-11,87); 3) "Placebo administration by a doctor with authority in the field" – 23,76% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 19,81-27,71); 4) "Placebo administration by any doctor provided that the patient believes in the effects of the preparation" – 23,76% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 19,81-27,71) of case.

Following the above mentioned, we conclude that most patients believe that it is more effective to administer a placebo without notice. To an equal extent, patients believe that neutral medication must be administered either by a doctor with authority in the given field, or by a patient who believes in the miraculous power of these preparations. Thus, the patient's expectations from the treatment are important, if he believes that this is an effective one, which will radically change his state of health for the better, the medication will have this similar result, but if the patient, believes that he will have negative effects on his body, whether they will cause adverse reactions or complications, these thoughts will bring with them the nocebo phenomenon.

As a control question, for a concrete attitude of the patients about the administration of the neutral preparations, the situation was presented to the patients in which they were "informed" that they had received placebo medicines for a certain period, for example homeopathic preparations, pills with pictures or special forms, neutral mixtures, prepared by the best specialists in the field.

Thus, the patients' attitude after they were "informed" about the administration of neutral medication instead of basic therapy, was divided into negative, neutral, satisfactory and good, with the preponderance of the satisfactory and good attitude (78% of responses). We suppose that one of the explanations would be the readiness of the patients to trust in the power of the medicine and that of the doctor.

At the same time, the Attitude of patients after learning about the administration of neutral medication was structured by: 1) "negative attitude - I don't believe in empty medicines" – 7,92% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 3,97-11,87); 2) "neutral attitude - I did not feel their effect at all" – 13,86% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 9,91-17,81); 3) "satisfactory attitude - some of them helped me some didn't" – 41,58% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 37,63-45,53); 4) "good - I felt that they helped me" – 35,64% (\hat{I}_{95}^{\pm} : 31,69-39,59) of case.

The data obtained outline the idea that patients have trust in placebo preparations and believe that this would bring beneficial health results. In order, to confirm this idea, patients were asked to express their agreement about the neutral medication using in a future medical practice. They scored their agreement on a scale from 1 to 10 (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Patients' agreement regarding doctors' application of neutral medication (placebo type).

From the illustrated graph we can see that patients demonstrate a certain confidence for the neutral therapy. From the 50 patients, 38 scored between 6 and 10 points. We assume that these opinions are since patients consider the therapeutic relationship important, which must be the basis of the medical act, also the way the patient perceives his illness, the way the patient reacts to the concrete pill or medication.

In order to analyse the affective particularities of the therapeutic relationship, with a potential placebo effect, the sampled group was proposed some questions with true or false response. These questions illustrate an integrative view of the entire placebo/nocebo subjects, as it highlights the fact that the brain changes the internal condition of the body. In other words, through the power of thought, those connections are formed in the body, which would lead to the complete remission or cure of a disease and, conversely, to the worsening of the patients' health, with the appearance of the nocebo phenomenon (tab.1).

Table 1. Patients' core beliefs about the placebo-nocebo effect.

Your thoughts can affect your health	True / 95	False/ 6
Positive expectations can improve health status	True / 95	False/ 6
Trust in the doctor and the prescribed treatment can add to placebo effects	True / 91	False/ 10
The placebo/nocebo effect is only visible in stress-induced illnesses	True / 41	False/ 60
The placebo/nocebo effect is only described in scientific research, not in real life	True / 20	False/ 61
A drug's appearance, shape, color, smell can contribute to the placebo effect	True / 65	False/ 36
Nocebo can cause structural changes in the body	True / 49	False/ 52
Placebo medication can cause side effects	True / 42	False/ 58

Not being notified about the administration of a medicine can result without effects	True/ 55	False/ 46
Placebo stops working when a patient knows about it	True / 75	False/ 26

From the obtained results, we deduce that patients are aware of the power of their thoughts and are disposed to apply the neutral medication if it will help them. The sick man believes that positive thoughts can improve his state of health, that his state of health will depend on the level of trust he has in the doctor and in the treatment he has prescribed. It is important for the patient the form in which the medicine is prescribed, the smell, the colour, but also the way in which the doctor recommends this medicine. The sampled patients believe that placebo is present in real life, even if the doctors do not inform them about it, they believe that the placebo/nocebo effect is present in all diseases, not only those related to stress or mental health.

Patients' attitudes and opinions about the role and placebo/nocebo effect in the therapeutic relationship can influence and shape both the relationship with the doctor and the treatment itself. The doctor, through his behaviour and professional competence, contributes directly and indirectly to the patient's response to treatment and to his confidence in the indicated medication. Otherwise, the image of the medicine is closely related to the image of the doctor, to the place he has in the hierarchy of the patient's representations. Depending on the degree of the patient's trust in the drug's effect, placebo therapy would lead to the remission or cure of the symptoms of some diseases, and, conversely, the adverse response - the nocebo phenomenon, with the worsening of the patients' health condition - may occur. The factors that determine the effectiveness of neutral medication can be divided into 2 groups: drug dependent and relational factors. Among the drug-dependent factors are shape, colour, smell, taste, form of delivery. Relational factors concern both the doctor (his authority) and the patient (his suggestibility).

The patient's belief in the beneficial or harmful effect of the drug directly influences the medical act and will shape the subsequent therapeutic results. The proportion in which placebo effects are registered in the population increases or decreases depending on the age of the population (young people are less placebo-responders, compared to the elderly), as well as the number of administrations and the duration of administration. If the patient's trust in the doctor and medicine is optimal, the somatic and psychological effects of the inactive substance with the appearance of medicine reach the highest values. Therefore, the therapeutic miracle comes from the patient's self, from his own pharmaceutical engineering, represented by trust, strength, goodwill and positivism, and is stimulated by a constructive relationship with the doctor.